

EU Relations with the Newly Independent States of the Former Soviet Space: Legal Backgrounds and Prospects

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Abstract: The paper focuses on legal fundamentals of EU external relations with the newly independent states that emerged after the dissolution of the Soviet Union in the light of the founding treaties of the European Union. The legal impetus for the European Communities to develop their cooperation relations with third countries, including the Soviet Union, relates to the Treaties of Rome. As a result it was concluded the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation. The concluded agreements in the 1990s with the newly independent states of the former Soviet space represent a natural development of cooperation relations established earlier. The new agreements provided distinct and differentiated approaches for cooperation with all fifteen states. The Baltic states concluded three types of agreements before the accession to the European Union: agreements on trade, economic and commercial cooperation; free trade agreements and Europe association agreements. As regards the situation of other independent states, it varies from signing or concluding only partnership and cooperation agreements to association agreements, including DCFTAs for three Eastern Partnership countries, without a clear promise of joining the European Union in a potential future. Legal backgrounds of cooperation between the European Union and the newly independent countries are analyzed, including legal effects of concluded agreements and prospects of future partnerships, which are crucially important for all involved parties. The adopted instruments of analysis are those of typology and chronology, concerning relations between the European Union and the newly independent states.

Keywords: European Union, external relations, newly independent states, agreements.

1. Introduction

The legal background for cooperation between the European Union and newly independent states of the former Soviet space has two aspects to be discussed. First, it is a matter following (a) the Treaty of Maastricht when the European Union got legal personality and (b) the dissolution of the Soviet Union that meant establishment of external relations with all fifteen newly independent states. Second, legal cooperation of the European Union with the newly independent states does not represent an incipient framework of collaboration; the treaty establishing the legal framework for cooperation in a past context was the *Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*. Considering the time when it was concluded, i.e. not too much time before the dissolution of the Soviet Union, it is fair to underline that legal effects of the treaty are scarcely noticeable. Only Russia could have benefited of a sort of experience as a legal successor of the Soviet Union. The other independent states had to start their external relations with the European Union from the very beginning, taking into account the line of succession in our case.

EU relations with the newly independent states have developed slowly and differently from country to country. The agreements have been concluded on EU elaborated legal texts, following the European values.

The investigation seeks to analyze legal backgrounds of cooperation between the European Union and the newly independent states, based on typology of concluded treaties, including the *Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation* to compare the state of affairs between the agreements of the European Union and the European Communities with third parties. This approach is pertinent from a double perspective. The temporal perspective comprises inherent changes on international and regional arenas. The actorness perspective deals with multiplication of subjects in international law. The approach

dichotomy is considered for the platform of discussions and analyses of cooperation relations that are governed by the concluded treaties between the parties.

2. The Treaties of Rome

If the Treaty of Paris constituted the beginning for further European integration, even in the field of steel and coal, the Treaties of Rome¹ represent indubitably a milestone for both deepening European integration and developing external relations of the European Communities with potential partners all over the world. The Treaties of Rome established new forms of international cooperation with third countries. The Treaties of Rome played a crucial role in preparing actorness of the European Union on international arena as well.

The legal basis for developing trade and economic relations of the European Communities with Eastern Europe resides in the exclusive competence (article 113 of the *Treaty establishing the European Economic Community*) by which the European Communities may conduct a common external commercial policy with third parties on behalf of the Member States. According to article 113, Member States “may not independently impose tariffs or quantitative restrictions on products originating in third countries; [...] they may not enter into voluntary export restraint or other trade agreements with third countries”². The European commercial policy is pursuant of the GATT rules.

Exclusive competence will be applied both to concluded agreement with the Soviet Union and the newly independent states.

3. The European Communities

Long before the agreements between the European Union and the newly independent states, there had been earlier pronouncements on relations between the European Communities and the Soviet Union that later split into fifteen sovereign peoples. These earlier legal pronouncements may be divided in EU (1) regulations, (2) decisions, (3) resolutions and (4) trade and cooperation agreements.

3.1. Regulation

Council Regulation (EEC) No 804/68 of 27 June 1968 on the common organization of the market in milk and milk products was the first act concerning potential relations between the European Communities and the Soviet Union³. The document had one introductory article; title I – prices – articles 2-5; title II – intervention systems – articles 6-12; title III – trade with third countries – articles 13-21; title IV – general provisions – articles 22-37. Namely it is the title III that prescribed common norms for the milk market and milk products of the Member States with third countries, including the Soviet Union. This regulation was followed by subsequent amendments for the time being in force.

Commission Regulation (EEC) No 863/91 of 8 April 1991 on the special sale of intervention butter for export to the Soviet Union and amending Regulation (EEC) No 569/88 was organized in 9 articles to ensure that butter is not diverted from its destination in third countries⁴. This is the first adopted European regulation addressed expressly to cooperation with the Soviet Union.

3.2. Decision

In 1998 it was signed the Joint Declaration on the Establishment of Official Relations between the European Economic Community and the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance. *The Council Decision of 22 June 1988 on the conclusion of the Joint Declaration on the establishment of official relations between the European Economic Community and the Council for*

¹ *Treaty establishing the European Economic Community; Treaty establishing the European Atomic Energy Community (Euratom)* of 1957 (not published in the Official Journal). The Treaties of Rome entered into force in 1958.

² David Kennedy and David E. Webb, “Integration: Eastern Europe and the European Economic Communities,” *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law* 28 (1990): 638, <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/16121164> (accessed 20 October 2017).

³ *Council Regulation (EEC) No 804/68 of 27 June 1968 on the common organization of the market in milk and milk products*, Official Journal L 148, 28/06/1968, 13-23, <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2c2cdf49-a24a-4502-b75f-aeafaefd09c/language-en> (accessed 20 October 2017).

⁴ *Commission Regulation (EEC) No 863/91 of 8 April 1991 on the special sale of intervention butter for export to the Soviet Union and amending Regulation (EEC) No 569/88*, Official Journal L 088, 09/04/1991, 11-14, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31991R0863> (accessed 20 October 2017).

Mutual Economic Assistance represented a legal framework for economic cooperation between the parties in their areas of competence⁵.

3.3. Resolution

In 1990 the European Parliament adopted the Resolution on Cooperation with the USSR and the Countries of Eastern Europe⁶. The act focused primarily on aid to East and Central Europe.

3.4. Trade and Cooperation Agreement

The European Communities signed a bilateral “first generation trade and cooperation agreement”⁷ with the Soviet Union in 1989. *The Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*⁸ was the first commitment of the parties to “establish direct contractual relations with one another which will permit further development [...]; creating favourable conditions for the harmonious development and diversification of trade and the promotion of commercial and economic cooperation in areas of mutual interest on the basis of equality, mutual benefit and reciprocity”⁹, considering that “the volume and structure of trade between the Contracting Parties do not correspond to the potential represented by their current levels of economic development and their future prospects”¹⁰. The agreement entered into force on April 01, 1990, with indefinite duration.

The Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation is organized in 6 titles and 3 annexes. The composition of the titles is as follows: title I – general – article 1; title II – trade and commercial cooperation – articles 2-16; title III – commercial and economic cooperation – articles 17-19; title IV – economic cooperation – articles 20-21; title V – joint committee – article 22; title VI – general and final provisions – articles 23-26. The annexes are as follows: annex I – List of regions of the Community and products referred to in the second indent of Article 8; annex II – List of regions of the Community and products referred to in the third indent of Article 8; annex III – Declaration by the USSR on the implementation of Article 17 (6). The titles and annexes are seconded by a Joint Declaration by the Community and the USSR concerning Article 23.

The Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation is an unprecedented historic act concluded by the European Communities and the Soviet Union, considering prior dissensions between the actors of the two military alliances: NATO and Warsaw Pact. The parties went beyond their previous divergent strategies in order to

⁵ Council Decision of 22 June 1988 on the conclusion of the Joint Declaration on the establishment of official relations between the European Economic Community and the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance, Official Journal L 157, 24/06/1988, 34-35, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ%3AL%3A1988%3A157%3ATOC> (accessed 20 October 2017).

⁶ European Parliament Resolution on Cooperation with the USSR and the Countries of Eastern Europe, Official Journal C 284, 12/11/1990, 47, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:1990:284:FULL&from=EN> (accessed 20 October 2017).

⁷ Paul Bardos and James Stamps, “Introduction to the Europe 1992 Program,” in *The Effects of Greater Economic Integration Within the European Community on the United States: Third Followup Report*, ed. John J. Jersic, 30 (Washington: United States International Trade Commission, 1991).

⁸ Council Decision of 26 February 1990 on the conclusion by the European Economic Community of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal L 068, 15/03/1990, 2-17, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1990:068:TOC> (accessed 20 October 2017).

⁹ Council Decision of 26 February 1990 on the conclusion by the European Economic Community of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal L 068, 15/03/1990, 3, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1990:068:TOC> (accessed 20 October 2017).

¹⁰ Council Decision of 26 February 1990 on the conclusion by the European Economic Community of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal L 068, 15/03/1990, 3, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1990:068:TOC> (accessed 20 October 2017).

develop peaceful trade and economic relations. The titles denote mutual commitment of the parties to explore their economic potentials for the benefit of their peoples.

According to *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*, there would be abolished by 1995 all discriminatory quantitative restrictions “with the exception of those concerning a limited number of products which might be deemed to be sensitive at that time”¹¹. Unlike other agreements concluded with Central European countries, the parties “did not make a specific commitment to achieve mutual concessions with regard to agricultural products, although the agreement is generally applicable to agriculture. The EC has therefore indicated its intentions to act more cautiously in reducing barriers to Soviet products”¹². The explanation for this caution is based on the fact that the Soviet Union was not a GATT member. It had a greater legal significance for the agreement between the European Communities and the Soviet Union than a mere reiteration of the obligations already assumed under GATT. In this case, it had a binding value for the signing parties. The Soviet Union “did not waive its right to deviate from its obligations in respect of substantially equivalent trade in the event that the EC re-imposed any quantitative restrictions lifted in accordance with the agreement”¹³. The agreement took into consideration the place and obligations of both parties by international law, especially the treatment in international trade.

The Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation also includes provisions on cooperation in the field of peaceful use of nuclear energy, considering the potential of the parties in this area.

3.5. In Brief

The basis for developing cooperation between the European Communities with third countries lies in the provisions of the Treaties of Rome that went beyond Member States bilateral relations. The European Communities may conclude agreements with third parties on behalf of the Member States. This is the legal instrument used in signing the agreement between the European Communities and the Soviet Union.

Cooperation relations between the European Communities and the Soviet Union developed gradually. It was possible after the Treaties of Rome (1957) that defined the competences of the European Communities.

The following acts prescribed cooperation relations between the European Communities and the Soviet Union until the collapse of the latter: (a) regulation – *the Council Regulation (EEC) No 804/68 of 27 June 1968 on the common organization of the market in milk and milk products; the Commission Regulation (EEC) No 863/91 of 8 April 1991 on the special sale of intervention butter for export to the Soviet Union and amending Regulation (EEC) No 569/88*; (b) decision – *the Council Decision of 22 June 1988 on the conclusion of the Joint Declaration on the establishment of official relations between the European Economic Community and the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance*; (c) resolution – *the European Parliament Resolution on Cooperation with the USSR and the Countries of Eastern Europe*; and (d) trade and cooperation agreement – *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation of 1989*.

¹¹ Council Decision of 26 February 1990 on the conclusion by the European Economic Community of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 11, Official Journal L 068, 15/03/1990, 5, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1990:068:TOC> (accessed 20 October 2017).

¹² David Kennedy and David E. Webb, “Integration: Eastern Europe and the European Economic Communities,” *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law* 28 (1990): 647, <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/16121164> (accessed 20 October 2017).

¹³ David Kennedy and David E. Webb, “Integration: Eastern Europe and the European Economic Communities,” *Columbia Journal of Transnational Law* 28 (1990): 647, <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/16121164> (accessed 20 October 2017).

The cooperation relations between the European Communities and the Soviet Union started with references in *acquis communautaire* and ended up with concluding the agreement on trade and economic cooperation.

4. The European Union

The external relations of the European Union with the newly independent states are characterized by diverse agreements of cooperation after the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991. They may be divided into those in which the European Union is the contracting party and those in which the European Union is the leading partner.

4.1. The European Union – Contracting Party

The types of concluded agreements vary from country to country in the newly independent states of the former Soviet Union. Immediately after the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the newly independent states started to build their statehoods and develop their external relations. Some of these countries succeeded to advance in their cooperation with the European Union, others adopted a moderate speed.

Out of all 15 new states, 3 of them became Member States of the European Union in 2004. It is about the Baltic countries – Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania. The other 12 countries are at different stages of cooperation with the European Union. Out of all these 12 states, 6 are included in the Eastern Partnership Initiative of the European Union: 3 Eastern European countries – Belarus, Moldova and Ukraine; and 3 South Eastern European countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan and Georgia. 5 countries belong to the Central Asia group – Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan. And 1 is a Eurasian country – Russia. The European Union has specific cooperation relations with all these countries.

For research and methodological reasons, the guiding principles in analyzing the agreements concluded between the European Union and the newly independent states follow a double perspective: (a) membership / non-membership; and (b) typology and chronology.

4.1.1. Integration through Membership

In the first category, there are included the newly independent states that concluded bilateral agreements with the European Union, including accession to the Union. This group of countries is formed of Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania or the Baltic states. They are among the first with which the European Union established diplomatic and cooperation relations.

4.1.1.1. Agreements on Trade, Economic and Commercial Cooperation

Before concluding the first agreements with the Baltic states on trade, economic and commercial cooperation, in 1992 the European Union included these countries in the PHARE Programme. This step represented a beginning stage in developing further cooperation relations.

It is in the same year – 1992 – that the European Union concluded: *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Estonia, on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*¹⁴; *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia, on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*¹⁵; and *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other part, on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*¹⁶. The agreements came into force in 1993.

¹⁴ Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Estonia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 1-9, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

¹⁵ Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 10-18, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

¹⁶ Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Republic of Lithuania on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 19-28, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

The agreements keep the same pattern for all addressed Baltic states. The composition of the agreements is the following: title I – general – articles 1-2; title II – trade and commercial cooperation – articles 3-14; title III – economic cooperation – articles 15-16; title IV – accession to international organizations and conventions – article 17; title V – joint committee – article 18; title VI – general and final provisions – articles 19-22.

The goals of the agreements are facilitation and promotion of “the harmonious development and diversification of trade between them, the development of various types of commercial and economic cooperation”¹⁷. The guiding legal values of the agreements constitute “respect for the democratic principles and human rights established by the Helsinki Final Act and the Charter of Paris for a new Europe”¹⁸.

The agreements strive at establishing trade and economic relations between the European Union and the Baltic countries. They can be considered primary acts in developing mutual cooperation in the fields of common interest.

4.1.1.2. Free Trade Agreements

The next generation of agreements between the European Union and the Baltic states refers to free trade. These are comprehensive acts on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Union and the Baltic states, being concluded in 1994: *the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Estonia, of the other part*¹⁹; *the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia of the other part*²⁰; *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia on trade in textile products*²¹; *the Agreement on free trade*

¹⁷ Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Estonia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 2, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 3, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017); Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 2, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 12, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017); Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Republic of Lithuania on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 2, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 21, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

¹⁸ Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Estonia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 1, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 3, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017); Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 1, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 12, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017); Council Decision of 21 December 1992 on the conclusion of an Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Republic of Lithuania on trade and commercial and economic cooperation, Article 1, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 403, 31/12/1992, 21, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1992:403:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

¹⁹ Council Decision of 19 December 1994 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Estonia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 373, 31/12/1994, 1-159, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1994:373:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²⁰ Council Decision of 19 December 1994 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia of the other, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 374, 31/12/1994, 2-65, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1994:374:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²¹ Council Decision of 19 December 1994 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the

and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other part²²; the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Lithuania on trade in textile products²³. Estonia concluded one agreement, while Latvia and Lithuania have additional agreements on textile matters. The free trade agreements came into force in 1995 and took the place of the trade, economic and commercial agreements.

The free trade agreements have the following composition: title I – general principles; title II – free movement of goods; title III – payments, competition and other economic provisions; and title IV – institutional, general and final provisions. List of annexes is specific for each Baltic state under discussion.

These acts were preferential agreements establishing free trade between the European Union and the Baltic states. The agreements are governed by the fundamental principles as: respect for human rights and for the rights of minorities, and for democracy; market economy; regional co-operation; implementation of a coherent political and economic reforms; dialogue. The major goal of the agreements was to establish free trade between the European Union and the Baltic states.

4.1.1.3. Europe Association Agreements

The last generation of agreements between the European Union and the Baltic states were on association (accession) to the Union. Europe Association Agreements were signed in 1995 and entered into force in 1998 after passing the procedure of ratification in all Member States. In the result of implementation of Europe Association Agreements, the Baltic states joined the European Union in 2004. These acts are: *Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Estonia, of the other part*²⁴; *Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia, of the other part*²⁵; *Agreement between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Latvia on trade in textile products*²⁶; *Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other part*²⁷; *Agreement*

European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia of the other, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 374, 31/12/1994, 66-211, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1994:374:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²² *Council Decision of 19 December 1994 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 375, 31/12/1994, 2-59, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1994:375:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²³ *Council Decision of 19 December 1994 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Agreement on free trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Atomic Energy Community and the European Coal and Steel Community, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 375, 31/12/1994, 60-199, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1994:375:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²⁴ *Decision of the Council and the Commission of 19 December 1997 on the conclusion of the Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Estonia, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 68, 09/03/1998, 3-187, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:068:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²⁵ *Decision of the Council and the Commission of 19 December 1997 on the conclusion of the Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 26, 02/02/1998, 3-96, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:026:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²⁶ *Decision of the Council and the Commission of 19 December 1997 on the conclusion of the Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Latvia, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 26, 02/02/1998, 97-243, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:026:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

²⁷ *Decision of the Council and the Commission of 19 December 1997 on the conclusion of the Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 51, 20/02/1998, 3-90, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:051:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

*between the European Economic Community and the Republic of Lithuania on trade in textile products*²⁸. Estonia concluded one agreement, while Latvia and Lithuania have additional agreements on textile matters. The free trade agreements came into force in 1998 and took the place of the free trade agreements. This was the third and last generation of agreements concluded between the European Union and the Baltic states before becoming Member States.

The Europe Association Agreements with the Baltic states were organized as follows: title I – general principles; title II – political dialogue; title III – free movement of goods; title IV – movement of workers, establishment, supply of services; title V – payments, capital, competition and other economic provisions, approximation of laws; title VI – economic cooperation; title VII – cooperation in the prevention of illegal activities; title VIII – cultural cooperation; title IX – financial cooperation; title X – institutional, general and final provisions.

The Europe Association Agreements provided appropriate frameworks to gradual integration of the Baltic states into the European Union. The Europe Association Agreements helped the Baltic states to achieve the goal to become Member States of the European Union. These agreements substantiated on respect for human rights, democracy and the market economy. Latvia and Lithuania were offered a transitional period for the process of reform; in the case of Estonia there is no mention of the transitional period. At the level of political dialogue, the contracting parties agreed on developing economic cooperation, strengthening the links, convergence, economic reform, promotion of peace and stability.

4.1.1.4. In Brief

Agreements between the European Union and the Baltic states were concluded speedily from one generation of agreements to another: 1992 – trade, economic and commercial cooperation, 1994 – free trade, 1995 – association (1998 – entry into force, 2004 – accession).

The concluded agreements between the European Union and the Baltic states contributed to full integration of these countries in the larger family of European nations. Later on, the Baltic states adopted Euro as national currency and became members of the Euro zone.

4.1.2. Integration without Membership

In the second category, there are included the newly independent states that concluded bilateral agreements with the European Union without a perspective for accession to the Union. This group of 12 countries is formed of Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan.

4.1.2.1. Partnership and Cooperation Agreements

The first agreements between the European Union and the group of 12 countries belong to the generation of Partnership and Cooperation Agreements. By means of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreements, the European Union supports democratic and economic development in the contracting countries. The Partnership and Cooperation Agreements enter into force for ten years after which they are automatically extended each year unless there are no objections raised or new (other) agreements concluded.

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreements with the countries of Eastern Europe, Southern Caucasus, Central Asia and Russia constitute a framework for political dialogue, strengthening democracy, developing market economy, encouraging trade and investments, aiming at providing a basis for cooperation in the legislative, economic, financial, social, scientific, civil, technological and cultural areas as agreed.

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreements signed with the group of countries may be divided as follows:

- 10 concluded / (being) in force – *Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of*

²⁸ *Decision of the Council and the Commission of 19 December 1997 on the conclusion of the Europe Agreement establishing an association between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Lithuania, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 51, 20/02/1998, 91-231, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:051:TOC> (accessed 23 October 2017).

Armenia, of the other part²⁹; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Azerbaijan, of the other part³⁰; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part³¹; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States and the Republic of Kazakhstan³²; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Kyrgyz Republic, of the other part³³; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States and the Republic of Moldova³⁴; Agreement on partnership and cooperation establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of one part, and the Russian Federation, of the other part³⁵; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Tajikistan, of the other part³⁶; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, and Ukraine³⁷; Partnership and Cooperation Agreement establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Uzbekistan, of the other part³⁸;

²⁹ Council and Commission Decision of 31 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Armenia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 239, 09/09/1999, 3-36, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:239:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁰ Council and Commission Decision of 31 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Azerbaijan, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 246, 17/09/1999, 3-38, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:246:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³¹ Council and Commission Decision of 31 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 205, 04/08/1999, 3-38, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:205:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³² Council and Commission Decision of 12 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Kazakhstan, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 196, 28/07/1999, 3-33, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:196:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³³ Council and Commission Decision of 12 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Kyrgyz Republic, of the other part, L 196, 28/07/1999, 48-77, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:196:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁴ Council and Commission Decision of 28 May 1998 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 181, 24/06/1998, 3-45, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:181:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁵ Council and Commission Decision of 30 October 1997 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Russian Federation, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 327, 28/11/1997, 3-46, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1997:327:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁶ Decision of the Council and of the Commission of 17 November 2009 on the conclusion of a Partnership and Cooperation Agreement establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Tajikistan, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union, L 350, 29/12/2009, 3-51, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2009:350:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁷ Council and Commission Decision of 26 January 1998 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 49, 19/02/1998, 3-39, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1998:049:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁸ Council and Commission Decision of 31 May 1999 on the conclusion of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement establishing a partnership between the European Communities and their Member States, of the one part, and the

- 2 currently undergoing ratification – Belarus³⁹ (signed in 1995); Turkmenistan⁴⁰ (signed in 1998).

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with Russia entered into force in 1997, with Moldova and Ukraine – in 1998, with Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan – in 1999, and with Tajikistan – in 2010.

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with Belarus was signed in 1995, but suspended 1997. One year later, an Interim Trade Agreement was signed and ratified only by Belarus (1996). An Agreement on trade in textile products between the European Union and Belarus on quotas was signed in 1993, being extended in 1995, 1999, 2003-2007 and cancelled in 2009. Instead Belarus is included in the EU's Eastern Partnership programmes. This is the framework of cooperation between the European Union and Belarus. A very reserved approach is because of respect for human rights in Belarus. Intensification of relations between the parties depends very much on this issue. Therefore, bilateral relations are still governed by *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation* in 1989, being endorsed by Belarus.

The Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with Turkmenistan (signed in 1998) is at phase of ratification as well, because the country failed to meet human rights benchmarks. So, bilateral relations were governed by *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*, being endorsed by Turkmenistan in 1994. Now the relations between the European Union and Turkmenistan are governed by *the Interim Agreement on trade and trade-related matters between the European Community, the European Coal and Steel Community and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Turkmenistan of the other part*⁴¹, signed in 1999 and entered into force since 2010.

Before concluding the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and Tajikistan in 2009, their relations were governed by *the Agreement between the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on trade and commercial and economic cooperation*, being endorsed by Tajikistan in 1994.

After the termination of the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and Russia, negotiations for a new agreement started, but suspended in 2010 because of the tensions between the parties.

To resume, the European Union concluded Partnership and Cooperation Agreements with a group of 10 new independent countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan, excepting Belarus and Turkmenistan due to objective reasons related to protection of human rights.

The European Union is either at phase of concluding new Partnership and Cooperation Agreements with certain countries, suspending ones or concluding enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreements with others.

Republic of Uzbekistan, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 229, 31 August 1999, 3-39, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:1999:229:TOC> (accessed 24 October 2017).

³⁹ *Proposal for a Council Decision on the provisional application of a bilateral agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Belarus on trade in textile products*, COM/99/0656 final - ACC 99/0260, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:51999PC0656> (accessed 24 October 2017).

⁴⁰ *Proposal for a Council Decision on the conclusion by the European Community of the interim agreement between the European Community, the European Coal and Steel Community and the European - Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Turkmenistan, of the other part, on trade and trade-related matters*, COM/2009/0287 final, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52009PC0287> (accessed 24 October 2017).

⁴¹ *Council Decision of 27 July 2009 on the conclusion by the European Community of the Interim Agreement between the European Community, the European Coal and Steel Community and the European Atomic Energy Community, of the one part, and Turkmenistan, of the other part, on trade and trade-related matters*, Official Journal of the European Communities, L 80, 26/03/2011, 21-33, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2011:080:TOC> (accessed 25 October 2017).

4.1.2.2. Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreements

*The Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Kazakhstan, of the other part*⁴² was signed in 2015. The agreement is aiming at building stronger political and economic cooperation in extended key policy areas between the parties. The agreement is to replace the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement. Kazakhstan is the first Central Asian state that concluded the Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement.

The composition of the agreement is the following: title I – general principles and aims; title II – political dialogue, cooperation in the field of foreign and security policy; title III – trade and business; title IV – cooperation in the area of economic and sustainable development; title V – cooperation in the area of freedom, security and justice; title VI – other cooperation policies; title VII – financial and technical cooperation; title VIII – institutional framework; title IX – general and final provisions.

The values of the agreement are democracy and the rule of law, human rights and fundamental freedoms and sustainable development; enhanced cooperation in foreign and security policy with the focus on regional stability, weapons of mass destruction, international cooperation in the fight against terrorism, conflict prevention and crisis management.

4.1.2.3. Association Agreements

Another stage of cooperation relations between the European Union and some new independent states is related to Association Agreements. The article 217 (ex Article 310 TEC) describes the association agreement as follows: “the Union may conclude with one or more third countries or international organizations agreements establishing an association involving reciprocal rights and obligations, common action and special procedure”⁴³. The Association Agreements are international treaties concluded between the European Union and third countries that create the legal basis that govern their relations. These agreements may prepare partners for future membership to the European Union or to enhanced cooperation⁴⁴.

The Association Agreements intended for Eastern European and South Eastern European countries are considered special agreements. The Treaty of Lisbon (article 8) prescribes the relations between the European Union and Eastern Partnership neighbours: “1. The Union shall develop a special relationship with neighbouring countries, aiming to establish an area of prosperity and good neighbourliness, founded on the values of the Union and characterised by close and peaceful relations based on cooperation. 2. For the purposes of paragraph 1, the Union may conclude specific agreements with the countries concerned. These agreements may contain reciprocal rights and obligations as well as the possibility of undertaking activities jointly. Their implementation shall be the subject of periodic consultation”⁴⁵. The special relations consider prosperity, good vicinity and peace, based on European values⁴⁶.

⁴² *Council Decision (EU) 2016/123 of 26 October 2015 on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, and provisional application of the Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Kazakhstan, of the other part*, Official Journal of the European Union, L 29, 04/02/2016, 3-114, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2016:029:TOC> (accessed 25 October 2017).

⁴³ *Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, Official Journal of the European Union, C 326, 26/10/2012, 144, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C:2012:326:TOC> (accessed 26 October 2017).

⁴⁴ More on Association Agreements, see Vasile Cucerescu, “EU-EaP Association Agreements: Legal, Political, Economic, Societal and Historic Implications,” in *EU Association Agreements with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine: Through Cooperation Towards Integration*, ed. Carlos E. Pacheco Amaral, Vasile Cucerescu, Gaga Gabrichidze, Ioan Horga, Anatoliy Kruglashov, Ewa Latoszek, Marta Pachocka, 103-106 (Chisinau: Print-Caro, 2017).

⁴⁵ *Treaty of Lisbon amending the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty establishing the European Community*, Official Journal of the European Union, C 306, 17/12/2007, 14, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:C:2007:306:TOC> (accessed 26 October 2017).

⁴⁶ More on Association Agreements with Eastern Partnership countries, see Vasile Cucerescu, “EU-EaP Association Agreements: Legal, Political, Economic, Societal and Historic Implications,” in *EU Association Agreements with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine: Through Cooperation Towards Integration*, ed. Carlos E. Pacheco Amaral, Vasile

So far, the European Union concluded Association Agreements with 3 Eastern Partnership states:

- Ukraine – *the Association Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part*⁴⁷;
- Moldova – *the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part*⁴⁸; and
- Georgia – *Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part*⁴⁹.

The Association Agreements include the following aspects: close economic and political cooperation (more than simple cooperation); creation of paritary bodies for the management of the cooperation; privileged relationship with the European Union; respect of human rights and democratic principles; intensifying the relations between the partners. In this respect, Gunnar Wiegand and Evelina Schulz underline that “the EU’s Association Agreements (AA) with the Eastern Partnership countries are designed to constitute a new stage in the development of the contractual relations between both sides. They represent pioneering documents based on political association and economic integration between the EU and its eastern partners, with the highest degree of mutual commitments. The AAs present a shared commitment to close and lasting relationships, based on common values. Thus, the AAs are a concrete way to foster a dynamic relationship between the EU and its eastern partners, focusing on support to core reforms, on economic recovery and growth, governance and sector cooperation. They envisage ambitious cooperation on home and justice affairs, including a perspective for visa-free travel. The AA also offers gradual integration with the EU Internal Market by setting up Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Areas (DCFTAs)”⁵⁰.

The accession provision is not in the Association Agreements concluded with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. Laurynas Kasciunas asserts that “the absence of EU membership prospect means that partner countries have no motivation to reform and come closer to the EU’s regulatory rules and standards”⁵¹. So, this type of agreements could be considered as atypical Association Agreements because of two reasons: (a) there is no explicit provision on the accession to the European Union; (b) it does not mean that joining is improbable, if the parties decide as such. It

Cucerescu, Gaga Gabrichidze, Ioan Horga, Anatoliy Kruglashov, Ewa Latoszek, Marta Pachocka, 106-112 (Chisinau: Print-Caro, 2017).

⁴⁷ Council Decision of 17 March 2014 on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, and provisional application of the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Ukraine, of the other part, as regards the Preamble, Article 1, and Titles I, II and VII thereof, Official Journal of the European Union, L 161, 29/05/2014, 3-2137, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2014:161:TOC> (accessed 26 October 2017).

⁴⁸ Council Decision of 16 June 2014 on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, and provisional application of the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union, L 260, 30/08/2014, 4-738, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2014:260:TOC> (accessed 26 October 2017).

⁴⁹ Council Decision of 16 June 2014 on the signing, on behalf of the European Union, and provisional application of the Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, of the one part, and Georgia, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union, L 261, 30/08/2014, p. 4-743, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L:2014:261:TOC> (accessed 26 October 2017).

⁵⁰ Gunnar Wiegand and Evelina Schulz, “The EU and Its Eastern Partnership: Political Association and Economic Integration in a Rough Neighbourhood,” in *European Yearbook of International Economic Law*, ed. Christoph Herrmann, Bruno Simma, and Rudolph Streinz, 335 (Cham: Springer International Publishing Switzerland, 2015).

⁵¹ Laurynas Kasciunas, *Eastern Partnership and Its Strategic Importance to the European Union* (Vilnius: Eastern Europe Studies Centre, 2014), 1, http://www.eesc.lt/uploads/Pranesimai/Kasciunas_Eastern%20Partnership%20and%20Its%20Strategic%20Importance%20to%20the%20European%20Union.pdf (accessed 26 October 2017).

could be a political game; but it could be a geopolitical game as well taking into account the vitiated respect of international law by Russia in Eastern Europe and South Eastern Europe.

However, there are Association Agreements, which are currently in negotiations with:

- Armenia (negotiations suspended in 2010 after Russia made pressures on national authorities to renounce to the Association Agreement and DCFTA)⁵²; and
- Azerbaijan (negotiations suspended in 2014, being invoked the frozen conflict)⁵³.

The only outsider of discussions on Association Agreements is Belarus⁵⁴. Advancement has not been done due to the fact that even the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement has not been concluded and implemented. This is a compulsory phase for Belarus before any negotiations on Association Agreement could commence.

4.1.2.4. In Brief

Integration without membership is applied to 12 new independent states: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan. Out of all these countries, only 10 concluded Partnership and Cooperation Agreements, excepting Belarus and Turkmenistan whose agreements are currently under negotiations.

The Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement was signed between the European Union and Kazakhstan.

Negotiations for a new agreement with Russia are suspended.

In the Eastern Partnership countries, 3 states – Moldova, Georgia and Ukraine – concluded Association Agreements with the European Union, and 2 states – Armenia and Azerbaijan – suspended negotiations for Association Agreements with the European Union.

Europe Association Agreements between the European Union and the Baltic states contained an express provision that the ultimate goal is to become a member of the European Union and the step towards association through these agreements will help the countries to achieve this goal. In comparison with Association Agreements concluded with Moldova, Georgia and Ukraine, such a provision was not included for these countries. It generates ambiguity, because there is neither a promise for joining nor saying it is unlikely.

4.2. The European Union – Leading Partner

In the light of European cooperation, it is worth mentioning two initiatives that refer to some newly independent states of the former Soviet Union. It is about the Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe (1999-2008) and its successor the Regional Cooperation Council.

4.2.1. Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe

The Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe (SPSEE) was constituted as an institution and instrument of cooperation aiming at strengthening peace, human rights, democracy and economy in South Eastern European countries, especially after the escalation of the Kosovo War. The Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe was established at the initiative of the European Union. The participatory status to this initiative was the following:

- Members: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia;

⁵² More on Armenia's Association Agreement, see Vasile Cucerescu, "EU-EaP Association Agreements: Legal, Political, Economic, Societal and Historic Implications," in *EU Association Agreements with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine: Through Cooperation Towards Integration*, ed. Carlos E. Pacheco Amaral, Vasile Cucerescu, Gaga Gabrichidze, Ioan Horga, Anatoliy Kruglashov, Ewa Latoszek, Marta Pachocka, 109-110 (Chisinau: Print-Caro, 2017).

⁵³ More on Azerbaijan's Association Agreements, see Vasile Cucerescu, "EU-EaP Association Agreements: Legal, Political, Economic, Societal and Historic Implication," in *EU Association Agreements with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine: Through Cooperation Towards Integration*, ed. Carlos E. Pacheco Amaral, Vasile Cucerescu, Gaga Gabrichidze, Ioan Horga, Anatoliy Kruglashov, Ewa Latoszek, Marta Pachocka, 110-111 (Chisinau: Print-Caro, 2017).

⁵⁴ More on the situation in Belarus, see Vasile Cucerescu, "EU-EaP Association Agreements: Legal, Political, Economic, Societal and Historic Implication," in *EU Association Agreements with Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine: Through Cooperation Towards Integration*, ed. Carlos E. Pacheco Amaral, Vasile Cucerescu, Gaga Gabrichidze, Ioan Horga, Anatoliy Kruglashov, Ewa Latoszek, Marta Pachocka, 110-111 (Chisinau: Print-Caro, 2017).

- Observers: Ukraine;
- Supporting partners: Canada, Council of Europe, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, European Commission, European Investment Bank, European Union Member States, International Monetary Fund, Japan, NATO, Norway, OECD, OSCE, Russia, Switzerland, Turkey, UNHCR, United Nations, United States of America, World Bank.

As it seems to be a larger coalition for promoting stability in the South Eastern Europe, the initiative was proposed by the European Union. Among the newly independent states as beneficiaries of this initiative were: Moldova (member), Ukraine (observer) and Russia (supporting partner). The status of a member (Moldova) and observer (Ukraine) was due to the proximity to the Balkans troubled region, on the one hand. On the other hand, the status of a supporting partner (Russia) was due to individual interests and geostrategic reasons.

4.2.2. Regional Cooperation Council

The Regional Cooperation Council (RCC) replaced the prior pact, being launched as an initiative for regional cooperation in South Eastern Europe. The Regional Cooperation Council functions “as a focal point for guiding, monitoring and supporting cooperation in South East Europe”⁵⁵.

The participating parties in the Regional Cooperation Council are: Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Canada, Council of Europe, Council of Europe Development Bank, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, European Investment Bank, European Union (represented by a representative of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy and a representative of the European Commission), Germany, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, International Organization for Migration, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, North Atlantic Treaty Organisation, Norway, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, South East European Co-operative Initiative, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, United Nations, United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, United Nations Development Programme, United States, World Bank.

Within the framework of the Regional Cooperation Council, the European Union is followed by more countries and international organizations in supporting cooperation in South Eastern Europe. Among the newly independent states only Moldova holds membership.

4.2.3. In Brief

The Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe and the Regional Cooperation Council have constituted indirect instruments of cooperation between the European Union and the newly independent states of the former Soviet Union. If the European Union has kept the status of participant in both initiatives, then in the Stability Pact for South Eastern Europe there were 3 new independent states – Moldova (member), Russia (supporting partner) and Ukraine (observer) out of which only Moldova became a member of the Regional Cooperation Council.

5. Legal Effects of EU Agreements

International agreements concluded between the European Union and third countries belong to legal binding instruments. As regards the typology of agreements between the European Union and the newly independent states of the former Soviet Union – partnership and cooperation agreements, trade agreements and association agreements – they make part of specific international agreements having a binding nature.

Partnership and cooperation agreements, trade agreements and association agreements concluded between the European Union and the newly independent states produce effects for both parties. As regards the partner party, the generated effects could be considered as “linear”, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, those affecting the European Union seem to be more complex due to the legal nature of the Union.

⁵⁵ *Statute of the Regional Cooperation Council (RCC)*, 2013, 1, <http://www.rcc.int/pages/95/statute> (accessed 27 October 2017).

When dealing with the agreements of the European Union, Mario Mendez emphasizes the maximalist enforcement hypothesis in chapter III of his book: *The Association, Cooperation, Partnership, and Trade Agreements Before the EU Courts: Embracing Maximalist Treaty Enforcement?* The scholar assesses preliminary rulings “where the bulk of EU Court activity has occurred (131 cases)”⁵⁶ and direct actions “commencing and terminating before the EU Courts in Luxembourg (53 cases)”⁵⁷.

(a) Mario Mendez identifies two core categories of challenges in the framework of preliminary rulings to:

- *domestic action* – provisions pertaining to trade in goods, movement of persons, a small generic category concerning neither of the aforementioned provisions; and
- *EU action* – provisions pertaining to protective measures; the European Court of Justice held that the provision of the article 15 “is effective only between the contracting parties and provides merely for a formal step to be taken after the adoption of protective measures... [and] cannot in any event be effectively relied on to contest the validity of the protective measures themselves”⁵⁸.

The scholar states that statistically there is a dissonance between judicial activity concerning challenges to domestic action (121 or 91%) and EU action (12 or 9%). He explains it through “the contrasting levels of judicial activity”⁵⁹, “the use of the direct effect lens”⁶⁰, “the actual nature and application of the direct effect test”⁶¹.

(b) As regards direct actions, Mario Mendez advances the opinion of “challenges to domestic or EU action allegedly incompatible with EU Agreements”⁶². The rate of challenges is as follows: infringement rulings (26 or 49%) and challenges to EU action (27 or 51%).

The jurisprudence of the European Court of Justice has made precise conclusions on legal effects of EU agreements, “nevertheless, the result is that it would be possible to suggest that to the extent that the maximalist treaty enforcement logic has been unleashed in the Trade Agreements context, it has, at least as a matter of practice, been so in a one-sided fashion in relation to the domestic action of the EU’s constituent parts. It is in this sense, above all, the Member States and their authorities that have had to grapple with the bold readings, and the implications for the domestic legal order, of this additional external, and now supra-constitutionalized, body of EU law”⁶³.

The majority of above mentioned cases belong to the period before the Treaty of Maastricht. After it, the agreements are characterized by more stability in terms of their application. It coincides also with the period when the European Union signed and concluded partnership and cooperation agreements, trade agreements and association agreements with the newly independent states.

⁵⁶ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 108.

⁵⁷ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 109.

⁵⁸ *Judgment of the Court (Fifth Chamber) of 17 October 1996. - Konservenfabrik Lubella Friedrich Bükler GmbH & Co. KG v Hauptzollamt Cottbus. - Reference for a preliminary ruling: Finanzgericht des Landes Brandenburg - Germany. - Common organization of the market in fruit and vegetables - Protective measures - Sour cherries. - Case C-64/95, European Court Reports 1996 I-05105, 17, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A61995CJ0064> (accessed 27 October 2017).*

⁵⁹ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 150.

⁶⁰ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 151.

⁶¹ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 152.

⁶² Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 158.

⁶³ Mario Mendez, *The Legal Effects of EU Agreements: Maximalist Treaty Enforcement and Juridical Avoidance Techniques* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 174.

The results of concluded agreements between the European Union and the newly independent states are aiming more at a process for transformation of these countries in terms of approximation, economic development, and consolidation of peace in the area.

6. Prospects

In order to draw a more or less picture concerning the prospects on relations between the European Union and the newly independent states, it is fair to have in view a twofold perspective: historical-legal and comparative approaches. It may be applied to all new independent states after the collapse of the former Soviet Union.

There is a clear set up of the principle of *coherence* in developing cooperation between the European Union and all 15 new independent states. Consecutive stages were assumed in concluding more ambitious agreements. It is coherence, on the one hand, and differentiation, on the other hand. The principle of *differentiation* was applied by dividing the ex-Soviet space in the Baltic states and the other 12 countries. Here the separation between them occurred. On this disjointing, scholar Bart Van Vooren refers: “During and after the dissolution of the USSR, the EC and its Member States differentiated between the CEECs and their ‘return to Europe’, and the NIS. Notably, for historical, socio-economic and political reasons relations with the NIS were placed on a weaker footing compared to the CEECs, and the EC did not conclude EAs with them [...]. These countries (except for the Baltic States which were treated as CEECs) were not offered Association, but instead were proposed PCAs”⁶⁴. The ‘alternative agreements’ expanded the gap between the former constituents in terms of political, economic and societal agendas. ‘Alternative agreements’ induced to fragmentation in the Eastern Europe.

The principle of coherence governs EU relations with the 12 new independent states, irrespective of their division: Eastern Partnership, Central Asia and Russia. Its consistency varies from case to case. Bart Van Vooren goes further and speaks about the concept of “coherence as policy synergy in the Eastern Neighbourhood Policy”⁶⁵. In EU external relations for the Eastern Neighbourhood, he also admits “equilibrium between soft law and hard law”⁶⁶.

The European Union’s policy synergy is not anymore in compliance with the dichotomy deepening-enlargement integration. Now the European Union has to focus on internal issues concerning socio-economic discrepancies, separatist challenges and Brexit dilemma. Deepening integration is likely to shape EU policies in a short and / or medium period.

7. Conclusion

All newly independent states have followed individual development ways. All of them have distinct legal systems. All of them have built peculiar cooperation relations with the European Union.

When treating all newly independent states, there are 2 basic principles applied to their relations with the European Union:

- Integration through membership;
- Integration without membership.

According to these principles of integration and cooperation relations with the European Union, the 15 countries may be grouped as follows:

- Member States (3): Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania;
- Non-Member States (12):
 - o Eastern Partnership states (6): Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine;
 - Concluded Association Agreements (3): Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine;

⁶⁴ Bart Van Vooren and Ramses A. Wessel, *EU External Relations Law: Texts, Cases and Materials* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 528.

⁶⁵ Bart Van Vooren, *EU External Relations Law and the European Neighbourhood Policy: A Paradigm for Coherence* (London & New York: Routledge, 2012), 225.

⁶⁶ Bart Van Vooren, *EU External Relations Law and the European Neighbourhood Policy: A Paradigm for Coherence* (London & New York: Routledge, 2012), 201.

- Unconcluded Association Agreements (3): Armenia, Azerbaijan and Belarus (this country is at phase of ratification the Partnership and Cooperation Agreement);
 - Central Asia states (5): Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan;
 - Eurasian state (1): Russia.

The three Baltic countries – Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania (now Member States) – concluded (a) Agreements on Trade, Economic and Commercial Cooperation, (b) Free trade Agreements and (c) Europe Association Agreements before joining to the European Union in 2004.

The remaining twelve countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan – concluded differentiated agreements with the European Union, i.e. Partnership and Cooperation Agreements, excepting Belarus and Turkmenistan (currently undergoing ratification). Kazakhstan signed the Enhanced Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with the European Union. Negotiations for a new Partnership and Cooperation Agreement with Russia are suspended.

Five of Eastern Partnership countries – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine – started negotiations for Association Agreements (without membership provision). Only Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine concluded the Association Agreements, including the DCFTAs. Armenia and Azerbaijan suspended their negotiations for Association Agreements with the European Union.

External relations of the European Union with the newly independent states – Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan – have developed differently from 1991. The Baltic states succeeded to be integrated in the European Union; the other countries still continue to develop cooperation relations of one or another type with the European Union.

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